

Study of Agility among Kabaddi and KhoKho Players

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study was to compare the agility among the Kabaddi and KhoKho collegiate players of Nashik. Twenty-four Kabaddi and KhoKho players (Kabaddi=12 and KhoKho=12) were selected by used simple random technique from the Nashik who represented them inter collegiate competition. Agility variable and Illinois agility test was conducted on Kabaddi and KhoKho players for data collection. Obtained collected data was analyzed by using independent sample t-test. Result shows that to compare the agility among Kabaddi and KhoKho players from results shows that there was significant difference among Kabaddi and KhoKho players. Therefore, set hypothesis there was significant difference between Kabaddi and KhoKho players was accepted. Concluded that there was significant difference among Kabaddi and KhoKho players which indicate the level of performance and also the findings of this study may be helpful to the kabaddi and Kabaddi and KhoKho players.

Keyword: Kabaddi & KhoKho Inter Collegiate Players.

Introduction:

Kabaddi & KhoKho is a fast and furious game of remarkable complexity, and the variety of skills displayed can confuse even the most knowledgeable spectator. At the highest level, these movements are the result of years of painstaking practice by players who have made many sacrifices in the interest of the sport to reach the game's premier stage. However, one of the truly great things about the game is the fact that it can be enjoyed by almost everyone with an interest in sporting activity. Kabaddi & KhoKho at any level is a thrilling game enjoyed by players of all ages. The vast majority plays the game primarily for social reasons and do not normally have the

opportunity for the sort of coaching that could significantly improve both their individual skills and overall performance.

Agility

Agility describes the physical ability which is fraction in time change body position and direction. In Kabaddi & KhoKho game situation, the tackle or control ability to start and stop to change direction Fastly and move quickly is a very vital factor and this type of quality decides one's performance level and the speed of acquiring any skill. High level of performance of Kabaddi & KhoKho player may depend upon the physical variables or Motor abilities.

Material and Method:

Method of the study

Study to the comparative research which was conducted with a purpose to see the difference of agility variable skill performance among the Kabaddi & KhoKho. Study was to compare the agility skill variable among Kabaddi & KhoKho players. To study, 30 male Kabaddi & KhoKho players (Kabaddi=12 & KhoKho=12) were selected as sample by using simple random sampling technique from the Nashik.

Selection of Variable

The study was taken to agility variable. For that variable measures Illinois agility tests used for collected data.

Selection of Tests

Table no. 1

Type of Variable	Criterion Variable	Test items	Unit of Measurement
Skill Variable	Agility	Illinois agility test	In Seconds

Procedure of the study

Subjects and given to them instruction about the need, importance description of the research explanation of Illinois agility test and Kabaddi & Kho-Kho players (Kabaddi=12 and KhoKho=12) were selected as sample by using simple random sampling technique from the Nashik. The selected subjects were conducted by Illinois agility test Kabaddi & Kho-Kho players, after the conduct test data was collected.

Statistical Tools

After data collection of Illinois agility test on Kabaddi & Kho-Kho players, by used analysis technique of independent sample ‘t’ test was drawn result. The level of significance was kept at 0.05 to test the hypothesis.

Results of the study:

The obtained results are present in the following table which represents the results of independent sample t-test to compare the mean value.

**Table no. 1
Descriptive statistics**

Group Statistics					
	Students	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Agility	Kabaddi	15	17.00	0.950	0.245
	KhoKho	15	19.06	1.006	0.259

**Table no. 2
Independent ‘t’ test analysis**

Variable	Variances	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means			
		F	Sig.	‘t’	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference
Agility	Equal variances assumed	0.209	0.651	3.168	0.868	2.06	0.357
	Equal variances not assumed				0.868	2.06	0.357

Discussion

The performance of Kabaddi and KhoKho has been influenced to great extent by skill ability variable of agility. Each player is necessarily required to be continuously on the move over a certain period of time. This puts a great deal of demand in terms of potential physical efforts on the part of each player on the playing field.

Discussion on the results of agility; It was observed from the finding that to compared the agility among collegiate Kabaddi and KhoKho players from table no. 1, shows that there was significant difference between Kabaddi and KhoKho players. Therefore, set research hypothesis that there was significant difference among Kabaddi and KhoKho players was accepted.

Sonia Titoria (2019), Comparative Study of Speed and Agility among Football and Hockey Female Players. Football and Hockey are a team sport, which requires maximum speed and agility for a longer duration.

Conclusion:

On the basis of the result obtained in the study the researcher made the concluded that there was significant difference between Kabaddi and KhoKho collegiate players which indicate the level of performance and also the findings of this study may be helpful to the Kabaddi and KhoKho players for improved the agility variable.

References:

- Arumugam, S., & Kumar, V (2019). Influence of Specific Field Training on Speed and Agility among Soccer Players, *International Journal of Scientific Research and Reviews*, 8(2).
- Baker, D. G., & Newton, R. U. (2008). Comparison of lower body strength, power, acceleration, speed, agility, and sprint momentum to describe and compare playing rank among professional rugby league players. *Journal of Strength Conditioning Research*, 22(1), 153-8.
- Dawes, J. (Ed.). (2019). *Developing agility and quickness*. Human Kinetics Publishers.
- Milanović, Z., Sporis, G., Trajkovic, N., & Fiorentini, F. (2011). Differences in agility performance between futsal and soccer players. *Sports Science*, 4(2), 55-59.
- Paul, D. J., Gabbett, T. J., & Nassis, G. P. (2016). Agility in team sports: Testing, training and factors affecting performance. *Sports Medicine*, 46(3), 421-442.
- Sheppard, J. M., & Young, W. B. (2006). Agility literature review: Classifications, training and testing. *Journal of sports sciences*, 24(9), 919-932.
- Yadav, S. K., Prajapati, S. K., & Mishra, M. K. (2015). Agility of high and low achievers' male hockey players of Banaras Hindu University: A comparative. *International Journal of Physical Education, Sports and Health* 2015; 1 (5): 23-24. (Online).
- Young, W. B., Dawson, B., & Henry, G. J. (2015). Agility and change-of-direction speed are independent skills: Implications for training for agility in invasion sports. *International Journal of Sports Science & Coaching*, 10(1), 159-169.